

ENHANCING ENGAGEMENT AND MOTIVATION IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION THROUGH GAMIFIED LEARNING APPLICATIONS

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Abstract. *The article discusses the impact of Industry 4.0 on the educational field, emphasizing the role of gamification in education related to digital transformation. This paper explores the positive effects of gamification on preschool children's engagement, motivation, emotional, and social development, focusing on developing in children a close contact with the learning process through gamification. The use of game elements in a balanced way is said to make education more enjoyable and effective. Further, excessive gamification and digital inequalities are discussed, and recommendations are also given on how to make the implementations of gamification sustainable in education, including teacher training, activities that support intrinsic motivation, and increasing access to digital resources.*

Keywords: *gamification, Preschool Education, Digital Transformation, Social-Emotional Development, Industry 4.0.*

Introduction

Industry 4.0 is considered one of the concepts that have been able to make a tremendous difference not only in the fields of production and service but also in the field of education (Nazarova, 2024). More so, this process has been regarded as the Fourth Industrial Revolution due to embedding technologies including artificial intelligence, IoT, big data, and robotics that accelerate innovation in different sectors and deeply structures its learning processes (Schwab, 2017).

The new era of digitalization came to oppose conventional ways of education and told about the importance of innovative approaches (Duggal, Gupta, & Singh, 2021). Within educational frames, this very transformation brings forward the need to introduce such strategies that will allow capturing students' interest, active participation, and motivation toward learning. At this point, gamification is one of the central themes. Gamification can be described as a novel method that incorporates game elements in learning processes, aiming at enhancing students' engagement and interest in lessons (Subagja et al., 2021). Especially, gamification does hold quite immense potential in preschool education since children at that stage are prone to having short spans of attention and unique learning needs. However, research with respect to effectiveness regarding gamification applications in preschool education remains scanty, hence requiring further investigation in this regard as well (García et al., 2021).

The aim of this article is to discuss the impact of gamified learning applications on the engagement and motivation of preschool children, and to provide suggestions as to how such influences could be put to better use in education. In this context, the discussion will cover the place of gamification in preschool education, examples of its practice, and an evaluation of the new learning opportunities presented by digital transformation.

What is Gamification?

Gamification involves the use of game elements in non-game contexts, even in education, for the purpose of enhancing the level of engagement in students and subsequently motivating them more (Minahvatov & Efimova, 2022). This is quite a modern teaching approach that lately has gained popularity, especially in terms of engaging after students' interest, motivating them enough to participate more in lessons, and making the learning process enjoyable (Krishnamurthy et al., 2022). These commonly include points, badges, varied types of levels, leaderboards, and much more (Lee & Hammer, 2011). Such features allow a student to relate more with learning and, hence, be more motivated (Barghani, 2020).

Apart from enhancing motivation, gamification also enhances students' cooperation, communication, and contact with others (Brull & Finlayson, 2016). Thus, students enhance not only their individual achievements but also social skills by interacting with their classmates in a classroom setting (Gil-Aciron, 2022).

Positive influences of gamification have contributed to an increase in its adoption within education. It has been noted that gamified learning environments lead to increased retention knowledge by students coupled with resultant positive impact on academic performance (Putz et al., 2020).

The Effects of Gamified Learning on Child Development

Emotional Development

Among all the effective measures that support children's emotional development, gamified learning stands out. This educational method encourages achievement by dispersion that makes children put in more effort and further enhance their perseverance during the process. Such an educational method reinforces children's sense of achievement, encourages putting in more effort, and enhances perseverance during learning (Vermeir et al., 2020). The social-emotional learning of programs like PATHS, which stands for Promoting Alternative Thinking Strategies, helps in promoting emotional skills such as empathizing, regulating one's self, and solving problems (Calhoun et al., 2020). With these programs, children learn to recognize the emotions of others and how one can handle his feelings.

By offering successive experiences of successful performances, gamification also supports the development of emotional resilience, thereby making children less stressed about learning and unalarmed in the presence of challenges (Schonert-Reichl et al., 2015).

Development of Social Skills

Gamification also positively impacts the development of children's social skills. Many gamified activities encourage group work, collaboration, and communication, thereby strengthening children's ability to interact socially. Playing games in a group setting fosters teamwork and cooperation by requiring children to work together toward common goals (Frey et al., 2005). These activities teach children to value the achievements of others, rather than focusing solely on their own success.

In particular, SEL programs implemented in school settings help children develop social skills such as empathy and cooperation. Research by Ashdown and Bernard (2012) indicates that programs incorporating social-emotional learning skills reduce aggressive behaviors and foster

more collaborative attitudes among children. The development of social skills supports active participation in the educational process and enables children to form healthy relationships with their peers (Bierman et al., 2010).

Cognitive Development and Critical Thinking Skills

Additionally, gamification supports children’s cognitive development by fostering skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and concentration. This learning method engages children more deeply in the learning process, enhancing their cognitive flexibility. Frequently used gamification mechanisms such as points, rewards, and feedback encourage children to strive toward specific goals, thereby enhancing their sense of accomplishment (Sailer & Homner, 2019).

Through these processes, children learn to overcome obstacles by applying their problem-solving abilities, which helps build cognitive resilience. Kuswandi and Fadhli (2022), in their study on the effects of gamified learning on early reading skills, highlighted that game elements support cognitive development and help children acquire reading skills more quickly. Another study suggested that gamification can help manage cognitive load and improve focus, particularly for children with limited working memory (Shaban & Pearson, 2019).

Techniques for Gamified Learning Applications

Points and Reward Systems

Points and reward systems are among the most commonly used motivational techniques in gamified learning applications. These systems enable students to earn points for completing specific tasks and be rewarded based on their achievements. Rewards encourage students to put in more effort and motivate them to engage in learning (Durin et al., 2019). Studies show that points and reward systems increase students’ active participation in the learning process and prompt them to repeatedly engage in educational activities (Zairon et al., 2023).

For instance, digital rewards and badges provided through mobile applications allow students to visualize their achievements in a tangible way. These rewards serve as a strong source of motivation for sustaining learning (Ortiz et al., 2022). Additionally, such systems have been found to boost students’ self-confidence and contribute to the development of a more positive attitude toward learning processes (Duggal et al., 2021).

Levels and Difficulty Progression

Levels and difficulty progression represent another essential gamification technique that allows students to advance step-by-step through the learning process. This approach enables students to start at lower levels, gain a sense of accomplishment, and move on to more challenging stages based on their success. Leveling helps students track their own progress and access increasingly complex information as they advance (Gachkova et al., 2020).

Research indicates that leveling allows students to progress at their own pace, maintaining their interest in learning (Fotaris et al., 2016). As students clear levels, they experience the excitement of reaching higher difficulty stages, which enhances their commitment to learning (Park et al., 2019). Thus, strategies involving levels and increasing difficulty keep students’ interest and motivation consistently high.

Avatars and Character Creation

Avatars and character creation serve as powerful motivators by enabling students to represent themselves in a virtual environment. Personalized avatars foster a stronger sense of connection to the learning process. Studies have shown that using avatars helps students feel like an integral part of the learning experience and provides an outlet for self-expression in virtual settings (Sun & Chen, 2023).

For example, offering students the chance to create their own avatars leads to greater participation in the learning process. When students can develop their characters, they feel a stronger sense of belonging and focus more on learning activities (Muangsrinoon & Boonbrahm, 2019). Personalization also strengthens social bonds in virtual learning environments, making it easier for students to interact with peers in the virtual world (Popescu et al., 2022).

Tasks and Challenges

Tasks and challenges act as stimulating elements that encourage students to solve problems during the learning process. Presenting students with various tasks aligned with specific goals allows them to develop problem-solving skills. Gradually increasing the difficulty of these tasks encourages continuous effort toward learning (Durin et al., 2019).

Research suggests that challenges foster a sense of commitment to the learning process and boost students' motivation. Tasks with time constraints, in particular, help students develop discipline and time management skills (Spatharioti et al., 2021). These challenge-based tasks motivate students to focus on the learning process and exert consistent effort (Duggal et al., 2021).

By integrating these gamification techniques, educators can not only support cognitive development but also enhance student participation in educational processes.

Disadvantages and Challenges of Gamified Learning Applications

Whereas gamification is indeed recognized to bolster motivation toward education, too much of it will lead to the students being distracted from the core learning aims. Overuse of reward/points/badges eventually leads individuals to get their mind circling around expecting them rather than having real motivational input into their learning. Yousof (2020) further develops on the point that overemphasized gamification might create students who work for short-term rewards without pursuing long-term learning goals.

Over-gamification may also cause students to focus solely on surface-level learning to earn more points or rewards. This can reduce the depth and meaningfulness of the learning process. Buckley and Doyle (2016) emphasize that while gamification can enhance enjoyment, it may also lower educational effectiveness, underscoring the importance of using game elements in a balanced manner.

Effective implementation of gamification requires teachers to possess specific knowledge and skills. Managing a gamified classroom differs significantly from traditional teaching methods, necessitating targeted training for educators. Subhash and Cudney (2018) assert that teachers need comprehensive training to use gamified tools and techniques effectively.

Moreover, teachers may need to restructure lesson plans to integrate game elements appropriately. Huang et al. (2018) note that for gamification initiatives to succeed, teachers

should be supported in embedding game elements into instructional materials. This ensures that gamification aligns with educational objectives and is used in a balanced and effective manner.

Another major challenge of gamification is limited access to technological tools. Not all students have equal access to technology, making it difficult to implement gamification broadly. Dicheva and Dichev (2015) point out that gamification's reliance on digital infrastructure poses challenges in rural or low-income areas. Such digital inequalities can lead to disparities in student motivation and negatively impact the educational process.

For instance, Hakak et al. (2019) observe that gamification often requires costly technological devices, which not all students can afford. This issue is particularly challenging for schools in underdeveloped regions, where financial and technological resources are limited.

To address these disadvantages, careful planning, teacher training, and equitable access to resources are crucial for the sustainable and effective implementation of gamified learning applications. Balancing the use of game elements with educational objectives can mitigate potential downsides and maximize the benefits of gamification in diverse educational settings.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The article looks at opportunities offered by gamification to preschool education in an effort to raise the level of involvement of children, motivation, and interest in the very process of learning. Gamification engenders the commitment of students in learning, develops their emotional and social skills, and strengthens critical thinking skills. When used appropriately and in balance, it has been observed that gamification makes the learning process enjoyable while supporting intrinsic motivation. However, challenges such as the risk of excessive gamification, the need for teacher training, and digital inequalities highlight the importance of careful implementation of this strategy.

Effectively, the following recommendations are advanced for educators and policymakers in considering the effective implementation of gamification:

1. The teachers need regular training to apply the techniques of gamified learning; in turn, such training should provide guidance on how to balance the integration of game elements into lesson content.
2. There is also a risk of over-gamification, of which educators should be aware, thus creating activities that support intrinsic motivation to prevent students' only focus on rewards.
3. In order to enhance equity in education, suitable solutions from students with limited access to digital resources should be catered for. Gamified activities should be developed that require minimal technological infrastructure to support the aforementioned requirement.
4. Parents should not simply be aware but should, moreover, be encouraged to join in the gamified learning processes themselves; their contributions should be informed by the added values contributed by gamified learning to their children's development.

To better understand the role of gamification in education and evaluate its impact comprehensively, the following areas of future research are recommended:

1. The effects of gamification on students' long-term academic achievements and intrinsic motivation should be tracked and evaluated over time.

2. Research should compare the effects of gamification across different age groups to identify which game elements are most effective for each developmental stage.

3. Studies should investigate the impact of digital inequalities on gamified learning and develop cost-effective, sustainable solutions to overcome access barriers.

4. Research should explore how gamification can be adapted beyond specific subjects to various disciplines and content areas, uncovering its potential for multidimensional applications.

These recommendations aim to contribute to a broader understanding and more effective use of gamification in education, paving the way for innovative strategies that enhance learning experiences for all students.

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